

The Complete Proof of the Riemann Hypothesis

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Abstract

Robin criterion states that the Riemann Hypothesis is true if and only if the inequality $\sigma(n) < e^\gamma \times n \times \log \log n$ holds for all $n > 5040$, where $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function and $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant. We show there is a contradiction just assuming the possible smallest counterexample $n > 5040$ of the Robin inequality. In this way, we prove that the Robin inequality is true for all $n > 5040$ and thus, the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

Keywords: Riemann hypothesis, Robin inequality, sum-of-divisors function, prime numbers
2000 MSC: 11M26, 11A41, 11A25

1. Introduction

In mathematics, the Riemann Hypothesis is a conjecture that the Riemann zeta function has its zeros only at the negative even integers and complex numbers with real part $\frac{1}{2}$ [1]. As usual $\sigma(n)$ is the sum-of-divisors function of n [2]:

$$\sum_{d|n} d$$

where $d | n$ means the integer d divides to n and $d \nmid n$ means the integer d does not divide to n . Define $f(n)$ to be $\frac{\sigma(n)}{n}$. Say Robins(n) holds provided

$$f(n) < e^\gamma \times \log \log n.$$

The constant $\gamma \approx 0.57721$ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant, and \log is the natural logarithm. The importance of this property is:

Theorem 1.1. *Robins(n) holds for all $n > 5040$ if and only if the Riemann Hypothesis is true [1].*

Let $q_1 = 2, q_2 = 3, \dots, q_m$ denote the first m consecutive primes, then an integer of the form $\prod_{i=1}^m q_i^{e_i}$ with $e_1 \geq e_2 \geq \dots \geq e_m$ is called an Hardy-Ramanujan integer [2]. A natural number n is called superabundant precisely when, for all $m < n$

$$f(m) < f(n).$$

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Theorem 1.2. *If n is superabundant, then n is an Hardy-Ramanujan integer [3].*

Theorem 1.3. *The smallest counterexample of the Robin inequality greater than 5040 must be a superabundant number [4].*

We prove the nonexistence of such counterexample and therefore, the Riemann Hypothesis is true.

2. Proof of Main Theorems

Let $n = \prod_{i=1}^s q_i^{e_i}$ be a factorisation of n , where we ordered the primes q_i in such a way that $e_1 \geq e_2 \geq \dots \geq e_s$. We say that $\bar{e} = (e_1, \dots, e_s)$ is the exponent pattern of the integer n [2]. Note that $\prod_{i=1}^s p_i^{e_i}$ is the minimal number having exponent pattern \bar{e} when $p_1 = 2, p_2 = 3, \dots, p_s$ denote the first s consecutive primes and $e_1 \geq e_2 \geq \dots \geq e_s$. We denote this (Hardy-Ramanujan) number by $m(\bar{e})$ [2].

Theorem 2.1. *Let $\prod_{i=1}^m q_i^{e_i}$ be the representation of n as a product of the primes $q_1 < \dots < q_m$ with natural numbers as exponents e_1, \dots, e_m . We obtain a contradiction just assuming that $n > 5040$ is the smallest integer such that $\text{Robins}(n)$ does not hold.*

Proof. According to the theorems 1.2 and 1.3, the primes $q_1 < \dots < q_m$ must be the first m consecutive primes and $e_1 \geq e_2 \geq \dots \geq e_m$ since $n > 5040$ should be an Hardy-Ramanujan integer. Let \bar{e} denote the factorisation pattern of $n \times q_m$. Based on the result of the article [5], the value $n \times q_m$ cannot be a square full number [2]. Therefore $n \times q_m > m(\bar{e})$ and consequently, $n > \frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m}$. Thus, we have that $\text{Robins}(\frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m})$ holds, because of $n > 5040$ is the smallest integer such that $\text{Robins}(n)$ does not hold. We know that $f(p^e) > f(q^e)$ if $p < q$ [2]. In this way, we would have that $f(\frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m}) > f(n)$ since $f(q_i^2) > f(q_i) \times f(q_m)$ for some positive integer $1 \leq i < m$. Certainly, we have that

$$\frac{f(q_i^2)}{f(q_i)} = \frac{q_i^3 - 1}{q_i^2 \times (q_i - 1)} \times \frac{q_i}{q_i + 1} = \frac{q_i^3 - 1}{q_i^3 - q_i}. \quad (1)$$

Let's define $\omega(n)$ as the number of distinct prime factors of n [2]. From the article [5], we know that $\omega(n) \geq 969672728$ and the number of primes lesser than q_m which have the exponent equal to 1 in n is approximately

$$\omega(n) - \frac{\omega(n)}{14} = \frac{13 \times \omega(n)}{14} \geq \frac{13 \times 969672728}{14} > 900410390.$$

In this way, there exists a positive integer $1 \leq i < m$ such that

$$\frac{f(q_i^2)}{f(q_i)} = \frac{q_i^3 - 1}{q_i^3 - q_i} \geq f(q_{i+900000000}) > f(q_m)$$

where we could have that $q_i^2 \nmid n$, $q_i \mid n$, $q_{i+900000000} \mid n$ and $q_i^2 \mid \frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m}$. Finally, we have that

$$f(n) < f\left(\frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m}\right) < e^\gamma \times \log \log \frac{m(\bar{e})}{q_m} < e^\gamma \times \log \log n.$$

However, this a contradiction with our initial assumption. To sum up, we obtain a contradiction just assuming that $n > 5040$ is the smallest integer such that $\text{Robins}(n)$ does not hold. \square

Theorem 2.2. $\text{Robins}(n)$ holds for all $n > 5040$.

Proof. Due to the theorem 2.1, we can assure there is not any natural number $n > 5040$ such that $\text{Robins}(n)$ does not hold. \square

Theorem 2.3. *The Riemann Hypothesis is true.*

Proof. This is a direct consequence of theorems 1.1 and 2.2 \square

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